

TRITICALE IS NOT ONLY A FORAGE CROP

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Annotatsiya. Insoniyat yerda 2 million yildan ortiq vaqt davomida mavjud bo'lib, bu davrning 99% dan ortig'i ovchi bo'lgan. Va faqat so'nggi 10 000 yil ichida odamlar hayvonlar va o'simliklarni ko'paytirishni o'rgandilar. Bizning bilimlarimiz ekinlarning rivojlanishini boshqarish, ularning oilasi bilan munosabatlari va bir qator takomillashtirilgan navlarda, shu jumladan tritikale yaratishda namoyon bo'ladigan xususiyatlarning irsiyatiga asoslanadi. Tritikale bug'doy va javdarni kesib o'tish natijasidir. Ma'lumki, tritikale madaniyati inson ongining mahsulidir, ya'ni tabiatda mavjud bo'lmagan texnogen o'simlik. Ushbu madaniyatni yaratishning asoschisi shotlandiyalik olim A. S. Uilson bo'lib, u birinchi marta 1875 yilda bug'doyni javdar bilan kesib o'tgan va steril o'simliklar olgan. Biroz vaqt o'tgach, 1888 yilda nemis olimi V. Rimpau birinchi unumdor bug'doy-javdar gibridini oldi. Keyinchalik 1918 yilda Saratov ilmiy stantsiyasida minglab bug'doy-javdar duragaylari olindi. Uning nomi Tritikum (bug'doy) va Secale (javdar). tritikale 1935 yilda nemis olimi Tschermak tomonidan yozilgan. O'zbekistonda tritikale faqat hayvonlar uchun ozuqa uchun ishlatiladi. Buni Prag-1 Respublikasida yaratilgan navlar tasdiqlaydi; naqsh; Mnogozernaya-2; Prag kumush em-xashak yo'nalishi. Ilgari bug'doy kabi bu ekinga qiziqish unchalik katta bo'lmagan, chunki respublikada paxta sektori rivojlangan. Yaqinda ushbu ekinning 750 dan ortiq namunalari bo'lgan O'simlikshunoslik institutida to'plangan tritikale kolleksiyalaridan erta va qurg'oqchilikka, issiqlikka va tuzga chidamli navlarni ajratib olish bo'yicha ba'zi ishlar olib borildi. Erta tritikale navlarini yaratishda ma'lum yutuqlarga erishildi, ayniqsa 1996 yildan beri CIMMYT bilan birgalikda ishlagandan so'ng, natijada agroekologik tadqiqotlar jarayonida yangi tritikale navlarini o'rganish va yaratish bo'yicha ikki tomonlama shartnoma tuzildi. naslchilik uchun yangi manba materiallari olindi. Qirg'iz olimlari bilan birgalikdagi ishlar natijasida yuqorida o'rganilgan istiqbolli tritikale liniyalaridan ikkita tritikale liniyasi o'tkazildi. Bir necha yil o'tgach, ikkala liniya, Alyosha va MISSIM deb nomlangan navlar. Qirg'izistonda ozod qilindi. Uzoq muddatli tadqiqotlar natijasida iqtisodiy jihatdan qimmatli xususiyatlari bilan farq qiluvchi meksikalik tritikalening bir nechta navlari aniqlandi. Ulardan ikkitasi Norman va Farhod 2000 yilda O'zbekiston Respublikasi SVTCGA o'tkazilgan. 2005 yilda O'zbekistonda chiqarilgan. Yangi Norman navi non pishirish uchun javob beradi. Bu navning pishirish sifati bug'doyga yaqin, chunki bu tritikale, ehtimol, tritikale bug'doydan ikkita genom va javdardan faqat bittasini olishi tufayli hosil bo'lgan. Shunday qilib, tritikale donidan nafaqat chorva mollari uchun konsentrlangan ozuqa sifatida va pishirishda foydalanish mumkin. Biz erta pishadigan, serhosil va turar joy, kasalliklar va ekstremal sharoitlarga (tuz, qurg'oqchilik, issiqlik) chidamli, yuqori sifatli, yashil va quruq vaznli navlarni yaratishni maqsadga muvofiq deb bilamiz. Ushbu maqsadlar uchun biz ushbu maqolada keltirilgan naslchilik uchun qimmatli manba materiallari sifatida istiqbolli tritikale navlariga ega bo'lgan viloyat seleksionerlariga tavsiya qilamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: ekinlar, tritikale, tabiiy resurslar, yaxshilangan navlar, nemis olimi, barqarorlik, ovqatlanish tartibi, SIMMIT, yangi nav.

Аннотация. Люди существуют на Земле более 2 миллионов лет, более 99% этого времени занимались охотниками-собирателями. И только за последние 10 000 лет люди

научились разводить животных и растения. Тритикале – результат скрещивания пшеницы и ржи. Известно, что культура тритикале – это продукт человеческого сознания, то есть рукотворное растение, не существующее в природе. Основателем создания этой культуры был шотландский ученый A.S.Wilson, впервые скрестивший пшеницу с рожью в 1875 г. и получивший стерильные растения. Несколько позже, в 1888 г., немецкий учёный W.Ritrau получил первый плодоносный гибрид пшеницы и ржи. Позднее, в 1918 году, на Саратовской научной станции были получены тысячи пшенично-ржаных гибридов. Его названия *Triticum* (пшеница) и *Secale* (тритикале) были написаны в 1935 году немецким ученым Tschermak.

В Узбекистане тритикале используется только на корм животным. Это подтверждают сорта, созданные в Республике Праг-1; Многозерная-2; Праг серебристый кормовое направление. Раньше интерес к этой культуре, как пшеница, был не столь велик, поскольку в республике был развит хлопковый сектор. В последнее время ведутся работы по селекции ранних и засухо-, жаро- и солеустойчивых сортов из коллекций тритикале, собранных в Институте растениеводства, насчитывающем более 750 экземпляров этой культуры.

Некоторый прогресс был достигнут в выведении ранних сортов тритикале, особенно с 1996 года после сотрудничества с СИММУТ, результатом которого стало двустороннее соглашение об изучении и разработке новых сортов тритикале в агроэкологических исследованиях. получен новый исходный материал для селекции. В результате совместной работы с кыргызскими учеными из изученных выше перспективных линий тритикале были переведены две линии тритикале. Через несколько лет обе линии, сорта получили название Алеша и МИССИМ, районированы в Кыргызстане. В результате многолетних исследований выявлено несколько сортов мексиканской тритикале, отличающихся хозяйственно ценными свойствами.

Два из них, Норман и Фарход, было переданы в ГСИ Республики Узбекистан в 2000 году. Выпущен в Узбекистане в 2005 году. Новый сорт Норман пригоден для выпечки хлеба. По кулинарным качествам этот сорт близок к пшенице, так как этот тритикале, вероятно, образовался за счет того, что тритикале взял два генома от пшеницы и только один от ржи. Таким образом, зерно тритикале можно использовать не только в качестве концентрированного корма для скота, но и в кулинарии. В этих целях мы рекомендуем региональным селекционерам перспективные сорта тритикале как ценный исходный материал для селекции, представленные в данной статье.

Ключевые слова: сельскохозяйственные культуры, тритикале, природные ресурсы, улучшенные сорта, немецкий ученый, устойчивость, режим питания, СИММИТ, новый сорт.

Introduction

Humanity has existed on earth for more than 2 million years, of which more than 99% of this period has been as hunters. And only in the last 10,000 years have people learned how to breed animals and plants. This has played a huge role in the evolutionary development of cultivated plants. Today's agricultural crops are the creation of those years. People would not be able to survive without them, as these are cultures selected by man. The last century was a significant period in history due to man's ability to manage natural resources to his advantage. Our knowledge is based on the principles of managing the development of crops, their relationship to their family

and the heredity of traits pronounced in a number of improved varieties, including the creation of triticale.

Triticale is the result of crossing wheat and rye. As we know, the triticale culture is a product of the human mind, that is, a man-made plant that did not exist in nature. The founder of the creation of this culture was the Scottish scientist A.S. Wilson, who first crossed wheat with rye in 1875 and obtained sterile plants. A little later in 1888, the German scientist W.Rimpau obtained the first fertile wheat-rye hybrid. Later in 1918, thousands of wheat-rye hybrids were obtained at the Saratov Scientific Station. Its name is Triticum (wheat) and Secale (rye).triticale received in 1935, which was written by the German scientist Tschermak.

Morphology

Triticale seedlings appear on the 5th – 7th day after sowing. During germination, three germinal roots are formed. The kidney coming out of the upper part of the embryo is covered with a vaginal leaflet – coleoptile. Once on the surface, it stops growing. The first real leaf breaks the coleoptile and comes out, forming shoots. The leaves are linear, green, with a strong waxy coating, large. The length is 25...40 cm or more, the width is 1.5... 3.5 cm. They consist of a leaf sheath and a leaf blade. The leaf blade usually falls off when the triticale matures, and the leaf sheath remains on the stem, mistaken for a leaf. Triticale is characterized by a high leafiness of the stem, reaching 43...57% or more. Unlike wheat, the upper leaves of triticale retain the ability to photosynthesize up to waxy ripeness. Forage varieties of triticale have larger leaves and stay green and juicy longer than those of cereals.

The stem is a straw, hollow, cylindrical in shape. It consists of 4 to 7 internodes, in most forms it is covered with a waxy coating. The stem length is 105...120 cm for grain varieties, 145...190 cm for fodder varieties. It depends not only on the characteristics of the variety, but also on the moisture and nutrition regime, the density of standing and the predecessor. In grain-bearing varieties, the stem retains its green color until waxy ripeness. The inflorescence is an ear longer than 15 cm. Dense, double-row, with separate spikelets on the ledges of the spike rod. The ear of triticale combines the multicolored nature of rye with the multicolored nature of wheat. There are 3-5 fertile flowers in each spikelet. 3-4 grains are tied, unlike 2 grains in rye. The spikelet and flower scales are lanceolate and narrow in shape, more similar to rye. The spikelet scales are hard and dense. The keel tooth can turn into a spinous appendage. There are spinous and spineless forms.

The grain-like, yellowish-brown, combining the characteristics of the parent species. The triticale grain is longer than a grain of wheat, and wider than a grain of rye. It has a longitudinal

groove on the ventral side and a tuft at the top. In appearance, the triticales grain differs from the wheat one by a more convex and oblong embryo. The surface of the grain is often wrinkled.

The root is fibrous, well developed. The root system consists of primary (germinal) and secondary (nodal) roots. The triticales root system, starting from germination, develops faster than wheat. Part of the roots penetrates to a depth of 100-150 cm. Triticales has a high ability to absorb nutrients from the soil.

Biology and development

Germination occurs at a minimum temperature of $+1...+3^{\circ}\text{C}$. The optimal temperature for germination is $+14...+16^{\circ}\text{C}$. During germination, germinal roots are formed. The coleoptile passes through the soil surface, and the leaf reaches the tip of the coleoptile.

Leaf development begins with the appearance of the first leaf from the coleoptile and continues until the deployment of nine real leaves. After the appearance of the third leaf, the growth of plants in height slows down.

The growth of the underground part, on the contrary, accelerates: underground nodes are formed, which are necessary for the further development of plants.

Tillering is accompanied by the formation of lateral shoots and a secondary root system. In total, up to nine tillering shoots are formed. During the tillering period, flowers and spikelets are laid. Triticales grows well, forming 3-7 shoots per plant, even in thickened crops, and in liquefied ones – up to 14-17 or more.

The tube begins at the moment when the first node is already visible on the soil surface. The plant passes to the generative stage of development. Intensive ear growth takes place inside the stem. After the appearance of the fourth node, the topmost (flag) sheet unfolds.[36]

The swelling of the ear is accompanied by swelling of the vagina of the flag leaf, above the ligule of which the tops of the awns are shown.

Earing begins with the appearance of 25% of the ear, ending with its complete discarding. The optimal temperature for earing is $+18...+20^{\circ}\text{C}$. Triticales has a longer period from earing to flowering (7-9 days) compared to wheat (2-5 days).

Flowering is noted when the first anthers appear. By the middle of the phase, 50% of the stamens mature. Flowering proceeds most favorably at an air temperature of $+14...+19^{\circ}\text{C}$ and good moisture supply.

The formation of grains begins from the moment of fertilization. With a watery grain consistency, the water content reaches 80%. During the period from milk to milk-wax ripeness, the moisture content of the grain decreases to 50%. The grain is soft, squeezed under the nail. The upper leaves and stem are still green.

The ripening of the grains covers the period of waxy ripeness (from soft to hard). In a state of soft waxy ripeness, the dent from the nail straightens, at a late stage it no longer does. The leaves and stem are yellow, the stems still retain flexibility.

The maturity of the plant means the full ripeness of the grain. The beginning of full ripeness coincides with the hardening of the grain, the moisture content of which is 17-20%. At late full ripeness, straw nodes are dry, grain moisture decreases to 16-17%.[36]

Features of development. The growing season of triticales is:

- 250 – 325 days for the winter form (including winter);
- 75 -120 days for spring forms.

To obtain an optimal harvest, it is necessary that triticale plants pass the total amount of positive temperatures during the growing season (from sowing to full ripeness):

- 1900 – 2100 ° C for winter form;
- 1800 – 2200°C is for the spring form.

Features of growth

The relation to heat. Triticale is undemanding to heat.

Frost resistance. Winter hardiness of triticale is higher than that of winter wheat, but lower than that of winter rye. Winter triticale tolerates frosts up to 18-20 ° C in the area of the tillering node. Spring triticale seedlings withstand short-term frosts up to –5-60C.

Attitude to moisture. Triticale is a moisture-loving plant. Its moisture requirement is higher than that of rye. The lack of moisture in the period from entering the tube to flowering leads to overgrowth. Moisture deficiency at the end of milk ripeness causes a decrease in the mass of 1000 grains.

Drought resistance. The drought resistance of triticale is higher than that of wheat, but lower than that of rye. The heat resistance of triticale is +37 °C. During grain filling, triticale tolerates drought and high temperatures well. This is facilitated by a waxy coating on the shoots, a developed root system and a high water-holding capacity of the culture.

Attitude to the soil. Compared to wheat, triticale is able to produce higher yields on poor soils. At the same time, some of its varieties are characterized by increased requirements for soil fertility. Triticale grows well in soils with a slightly acidic or neutral reaction of the medium (pH 5.8–7.0).

Favorable soils. The best results can be obtained when cultivating triticale on cohesive soils with a humus content of at least 1.8%, P₂O₅ and K₂O of at least 150 mg/kg of soil.

Currently, the main producers of triticale are Poland, Germany and France

Country	2005	2014	2017	2018	2020	2022
Poland	3748	5200	5102	4086	6080	5440
Germany	2676	3000	2397	1936	2036	1930
French	1793	2000	1448	1382	1310	1614
Belorus	1121	2100	1642	1015	1543	1193
Spain	52	400	551	649	600	635
China	1350	500	689	774	356	386
Turkey	110				276	320
Russia	0	700	619	401	338	307
Austria	198		323	279	347	293
Czech	255				213	208
Lithuania	201	400	331	337	449	205
Romania	94				236	192
Hungary	566	500	480	330	326	186
Sweden	272				167	163
Total	13503		15564	12803	13437	

Today's triticale is an art in science and applied breeding. This is due to a process achieved by scientists from Poland, Canada, the USA and Mexico. SIMMIT

During its use as a commercial crop in agriculture, the visibility and qualities of triticale have changed. In the beginning, the plants were tall, fruitless (i.e. infertile) and matured late, and they also had shriveled grains that were not commercially unacceptable.

Technical methods for the production of primary triticale and the creation of a genetic variety opened the door to direct genetic improvement, especially after 1965, when the triticale program was launched at the CIMMYT organization.

At first, this crop attracted the attention of foragers as a powerful tall crop that was resistant to lodging and diseases, and gave a large volume of green mass, even in poor soil.

In Uzbekistan, triticale is used exclusively for animal feed. This is evidenced by the varieties created in the Republic of Prag-1; Pattern; Mnogozernaya-2; Prag silvery fodder direction. Interest in this crop used to be not so great, as well as wheat, because the cotton sector was developed in the republic.

After the independence of the Republic, the Laws of the Republic on Grain Independence were adopted. The acreage of grain has increased dramatically from year to year. Currently, more than 1 million hectares of grain crops are sown in the Republic under irrigation, especially wheat. However, the acreage of triticale remains insignificant today. Mainly, crop crops with alfalfa prevail, which gives a high green mass in the first mowing.

Recently, some work has been carried out to isolate precocious and drought-, heat- and salt-resistant varieties from the collections of triticale concentrated in the Institute of Crop Production, which has more than 750 samples of this crop.

Certain successes have been achieved in the creation of precocious triticale varieties, especially after working together with CIMMYT Since 1996, a bilateral agreement has been concluded on the study and creation of new triticale varieties in the process of agroecological study as a result. a new source material for breeding was obtained.

Some of the studied cultivars exceeded the standard varieties in terms of biological and economically valuable characteristics in terms of precocity by an average of 12-16 days, in terms of earing, they are 21-24 days ahead of the standard almost at the level of wheat and barley. These samples were studied during control in competitive variety tests Triticale samples distinguished by economically valuable characteristics for drought, heat and salt resistance are presented in Table 1.

The nature of germination of seeds of promising Mexican triticale samples in solutions-osmotic and after warming up.

Number of accessions	The percentage of germination of seeds						
	Control	on sucrose		NaCl		after warming up	
		13,70%	15,80%	1,40%	1,82%	56 ⁰ C	58 ⁰ C
Mnogozernaya-2 (control)	100	83	95	93	90	45	40
571870	100	98	68	92	97	60	54
571873	100	91	78	96	88	70	62
571876	99	92	71	99	95	84	76
571877	99	94	89	99	87	72	70
571878	97	97	93	98	95	58	55
571883	98	98	91	95	96	66	57
571885	100	98	32	97	98	76	70
571887	100	100	81	99	97	94	90
571888	100	82	95	97	97	76	58

571895	99	94	91	100	95	94	80
572123	100	81	90	99	91	54	47
571884	100	88	92	99	92	60	52

Resistance group for sucrose and NaCl-

- I- highly resistant from 70-100%,
- II- II- medium-resistant from 31-69%,
- III- III-weakly resistant from 0.0-30%.

Resistance group after warming seeds:

- I-highly resistant- from 47-100%,
- II-medium-resistant-from 24-47%,
- III-weakly resistant from 0.0-24%.

The results of the data obtained show that these samples simultaneously have group I resistance to these factors.

As a result of joint work with Kyrgyz scientists, two triticale lines were transferred from the above-studied promising triticale lines. After several years of studying both lines, varieties called Alyosha and MISSIM. were released in Kyrgyzstan.

As a result of long-term study, several varieties of triticale of Mexican origin have been identified, which differ in their economically valuable characteristics. Two of them, Norman and Farhad, were transferred to the SVTC of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2000. Which were released in Uzbekistan in 2005.

The above mentioned samples were analyzed for baking qualities at the Williams Kazakh Institute of Agriculture (Table 2). The chemical composition of the grain of these varieties is more similar to wheat than rye, except for the free sugar content and this is closer to the composition of rye. The size, shape and color of the grain has more similarities with wheat than with rye. These varieties have smooth grain. In ordinary varieties, it is wrinkled. These are wheat-like ingredients.

The new Norman variety is suitable for baking bread. The baking qualities of this variety are close to wheat, since this triticale was probably formed due to the fact that triticale receives two genomes from wheat and only one from rye. Thus, triticale grain can be used not only as a concentrated feed for livestock and in baking.

Table 2.

Physico-chemical and baking qualities of triticale varieties

Variety	Grain size, g/l	General vitreous, %	Content, %		Indications of IDK-1, units.	Dough formation time, min.	The volume of baking from 100gr. flour	Appearance of bread, score	Porosity, (ball)	Total baking score, (ball)
			protein	Raw gluten						
Kissa	796	53	12,9	22	105	1,5	490	3	2,5	2,74
Armino Norman	784	55	13,2	21,6	95	1,54	580	4	4	3,6
Shacal	775	31	11,5	13,2	68	1	555	4	4	3,46

Sonni	776, 5	60	13,9	22,4	95	2	640	4,5	4,5	4,14
Farhad	728, 5	34	14,3	22,8	100	1,5	540	2	2	2,24
St. Unumly bugdai (wheat)	813	72	12,8	28,4	90	2,5	800	3,5	3,5	3,76

This will give a wide green road to the expansion of triticale acreage in the conditions of irrigated agriculture in Central Asia. The grain yield of some studied triticale varieties under irrigation conditions in Uzbekistan is 90-97 kg/ha, which is significantly more than the varieties released here.

We consider it advisable to create early-ripening, high-yielding, and resistant to lodging, diseases and extreme conditions (salt, drought, heat) varieties with high grain quality, green and dry weight. For these purposes, we recommend it to breeders of the region has promising triticale cultivars as a valuable source material for breeding given in this paper.

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